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A Study of Application of Learning Management System (LMS) MOODLE in Communication of Information – A Literature Review

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Abstract

In 21st Century, development in the digital technologies has brought different tools for making communication better and helped learners in improving their learning and achievements. Among this one of the most widely tool for communication in teaching and learning is Learning Management System(LMS), there are many Learning Management System used by the Universities and Colleges such as MOODLE, Blackboard, Docebo, but from these MOODLE is free and Open Source Software. In this paper a literature review was done on the LMS, MOODLE for finding its application in communicating of information. After review and analysis from different sources such as, DOAJ, Google Scholar, Academia, Science Direct, it was concluded that MOODLE has tools which communicates information effectively, 24/7, fast and it is cost effective.

An eLearning platform is widely used in the smart classrooms, as it provides fastest, cost-effective and consistent communication between the teachers and learners. In the traditional classroom teaching information is delivered through the use of tools such as presentation software and power points, but these tools are static and are not much effective in teaching and communicating these tools also does not enhance learning among the learners (Ebarido & Valderama, 2009). But modern E-learning sites and LMS are dynamic and have high quality content and instructional design that makes learning and communication most effective. In the present study researcher has reviewed research articles which has found MOODLE has communications tools which are most effective tools in communicating information and are widely used in the Distance Learning, Universities, College and Schools but there are also research findings which suggests Face to Face communication as most effective and preferred by the Universities, Colleges and Schools, but with limitations as being not available 24/7 to the learners.

Keywords: MOODLE, Learning Management System (LMS), eLearning, Online Learning,

Objectives of the Study

The problem investigated in this research related with studying the Use of Learning Management System (LMS) MOODLE for communication of information by the learners, teachers and institutes.

Its objectives were to:

- Review the Use of MOODLE tools in sharing the digital resources by teachers and learners.
- Study the Use of MOODLE tools by teachers and learners in collaborating learning, through literature review.
- Study the Use of MOODLE tools by teachers and learners in communication in an online learning, through literature review.

Methods adopted

In this research analysis of literature is done by using data base of Google Scholar, Online Journals, Academia, Google Search Engines, Openeducational resources and Websites. The openeducational research source Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is searched for finding Abstracts and Journals to study applications of MOODLE for Communication of Information between learners, teachers and Institutes. By using the following combinations of key words "MOODLE and Use/Applications", "MOODLE and Communications", "Effectiveness and MOODLE", "Educational use of MOODLE", "MOODLE and Effective Teaching Learning", "MOODLE and Collaboration", and "MOODLE and Learning", a data base is analyzed to study the Applications of MOODLE. In these search more than 120 studies has been identified, which uses MOODLE and its tools in communication of information. Beside Journals other useful database such as Reference Books, Reference Sources, and Reports, Websites and Handbooks on Research, are also reviewed for the study of Web 2.0 tools.

Literature Review and Analysis of Literature

In their study (Chaurasia, Soni, Studies, & Manager, 2011), has concluded that the various supports and tools offered by MOODLE for E-learning are used by the learners and teachers. MOODLE is an effective and useful tool which helps tutors by creating a platform to save teaching and learning material easily and a communicating and collaborative online platform for teachers and learners to learn together. Besides creating courses, it is also very useful to join the online communities to keep yourself updated with the world and to know a circle of scholars that will truly encircle the globe. They have also observed that the website www.moodle.org provides a lot of modules, which are very useful for the communications and collaborations. These tools help us to make teaching and learning more effective. Further they observe that, the implementation of the information and communication technology in education with e-learning through MOODLE, allows improving effectiveness of the education. E-learning allows better cooperation among the learners, the tutors and the students. The accessibility, usability and student collaborative learning can be improved and higher motivation among the students and the teachers can be achieved with LMS MOODLE. As observed by (Al-ani, 2013), the LMS, MOODLE in teaching and learning has more impact on student-centered learning techniques that make students more active and motivated. In this research it was also observed that the

students also demonstrate a greater willingness to share, communicate and collaborate with their peers and teachers by using MOODLE.

In his study (Baig, 2011b), observed that the Website 'Wiziq.com' provides online tools for communication of information and therefore it is used for the study of effectiveness of online learning on students' achievement. In this study researcher found A high score in achievement among students' taught and studied through online tools and online learning environment which was used as a learning tool for communication and collaboration of information. Similarly achievement among students of F2F teaching was found low, this is because in F2F learning, collaborating and sharing of resources is limited to the walls of classroom, but online learning made possible to learning, collaborating, and sharing of resources beyond four walls. Online learning environment provides features such as, user center, user control and communication, and making teaching learning process learner centric.

A Study was conducted on MOODLE and the tools by (Martín-Blas & Serrano-Fernández, 2009), has found that, MOODLE and its tools are a great way for teachers to organize, manage and deliver course materials. From the didactic point of view, the usage of multimedia tools to create attractive activities makes the learning process friendlier for students. As a consequence, these activities increase the interest of the students in the study of Physics. Teachers can provide students with a great amount of resources that usually they cannot show in the classroom due to the lack of time. Moodle also makes easier the interaction with the students in real-time and also allows receiving their opinions and suggestions; as a learning community, Moodle makes possible for students to share their knowledge and difficulties, so they can help each other via forums and chats. Teachers can notice in which parts of the subject they have more difficulties to understand the concepts developed in the classroom. In this study it was found that students were a bit reluctant to participate in this activity at the beginning, probably because they were not used to face new tasks. Then, they gradually increased their visits to the site. Learners started to begin to explore the site when Lectures were uploaded and then they started doing the quizzes and they also suggested some improvements. This is a key point, as it is very important that the students feel involved in their own learning process, and it has been noticed that the number of visits to the platform is increasing over time which suggests that the students have interest in such MOODLE. The findings by (Martín-Blas & Serrano-Fernández, 2009), suggests that, the improvement of the academic results derived from the use of this e-learning platform has been improved. It was also observed by the Researcher that the students who used MOODLE regularly during the semester have obtained higher scores than the students who did not. So the impact for students of the MOODLE have become apparent.

According to (Wu, 2008), MOODLE is a free and user-friendly LMS, which can greatly help English writing teachers flexibly manage and edit their teaching materials, access students' assignments easily, and significantly promote synchronous and asynchronous communication between students and teachers. (Wu,

2008) states that, though MOODLE, is a useful tool for communication and collaboration of information but also criticizes that, it is not designed specifically for English writing courses, further he suggest that English writing teachers at tertiary institutes, MOODLE would be a perfect teaching tool if some editable 'comment bank' modules could be added by instructors so that teachers could easily use the drop-down menu to give 'canned comments'.

In his research findings and analysis of communication tools (Baig, 2011a), observed that learners performance gets enhances by MOODLE and its tools, these tools made possible for the learners to communicate, collaborate and share information 24 /7 with creating, editing, tagging and rating content instantaneously, thus making interaction among learners in an exciting way, besides this learner can communicate with their teachers as well a co-learners synchronously as well as asynchronously, therefore MOODLE is a dynamic useful and versatile tool used for communicating information.

Findings

In this research an analysis of literature review has been done by using data base from Open Education Research, DOAJ, Google Scholars, Google Books, E-books, and Websites and it was found that MOODLE and its tools are very useful for the learners, teachers and institutes in communication and collaboration of information, thus Distance Education learners gets an opportunity to communicate information through features present in MOODLE. Thus MOODLE made possible for the learners to communicate, collaborate and share information 24 hours a day and 7 days in a week and the tools also communicate synchronously as well as asynchronously therefore MOODLE is a dynamic and versatile tool used for communicating information. MOODLE is an effective, dynamic, versatile and useful tool which helps tutors by creating a platform to store information through cloud and it is easy to use for communicating and collaborating by the teachers and learners to learn together.

Conclusions

MOODLE is the most widely used LMS among Learners, Teachers and Institutes for communicating, sharing and collaborating. MOODLE is easy to use, popular, flexible, and cost effective. MOODLE help learners and teachers to acquire education and learning without any hassle and hence they are the most widely used and popular among learners. In this review of research findings suggests that tools in MOODLE facilitates communication among learners and its tools such as Emails, Posts, Messages, Discussion Forums, Notes, Upcoming Events, Wikis, and Chats are used Synchronously as well as Asynchronously by the teacher and learners. There are other applications such as documents and webpages which displays information to the learners so that they can access it asynchronously. Applications such text messaging and instant messaging also helps learners to share information synchronously in the real time and these applications are free to use. Sharing of information is possible in the MOODLE with applications such as share posts and subscriptions

from different users and groups. Beside communication other tools such as Web Links, YouTube, Wikipedia, Wiki Books, Google Books, and Online Journals can also be embedded in the MOODLE and use for sharing and communicating information. Thus MOODLE is a very Useful, Versatile, Dynamic LMS for communication of information hence it is popular and widely used in the Distance Learning and Blended Mode of learning.

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